

**THE ROLE OF TOURISM EXPORT OF UZBEKISTAN ON THE IMPROVEMENT OF
WORLD INTERNATIONAL RANKS****Bekmurodova F.A**

PHD candidate of economics in the University of World Economy and Diplomacy

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10139243>

***Annotatsiya.** O'zbekistonning xalqaro reytinglardagi o'rnini yaxshilashdagi eng muhim sohalardan biri turizm hisoblanadi. Turizm eksportini rivojlantirish O'zbekiston uchun iqtisodiy o'sishga va bundan tashqari bir nechta muhim makroiqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlarning yaxshilanishiga sabab bo'ladi. Bundan tashqari, O'zbekiston uchun xalqaro turizm reytinglaridagi o'rnini yaxshilashga imkon yaratdi. Ushbu maqola turizm sohasining O'zbekistondagi hozirgi holati va uni xalqaro standartlarga yetkazish uchun qilinishi kerak bo'lgan vazifalar haqida tahlil qiladi.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** turizm eksport, segment, T&T Yalpi Ichki Mahsulotdagi ulushi, turizm xarajatlari.*

***Аннотация.** Туризм является одним из важнейших направлений улучшения позиций Узбекистана в международных рейтингах. Развитие туристического экспорта приведет к экономическому росту Узбекистана и, кроме того, к улучшению ряда важных макроэкономических показателей. Кроме того, это позволило Узбекистану улучшить свои позиции в международных туристических рейтингах. В данной статье анализируется современное состояние туризма в Узбекистане и задачи, которые необходимо решить для его доведения до международных стандартов.*

***Ключевые слова:** туристический экспорт, сегмент, доля T&T ВВП, расходы на туризм.*

***Abstract.** Tourism is one of the most important areas in improving Uzbekistan's position in international rankings. The development of tourism exports will lead to economic growth for Uzbekistan and, in addition, to the improvement of several important macroeconomic indicators. In addition, it made it possible for Uzbekistan to improve its position in international tourism rankings. This article analyzes the current state of tourism in Uzbekistan and the tasks that must be done to bring it up to international standards.*

***Keywords:** tourism export, segment, share of T&T GDP, tourism expenditure.*

Tourism is one of the developing key industries in the world, being important for developing countries, especially for Uzbekistan. One of the main tasks shown in the New Strategy of Development for 2023-2030 is increasing share of tourism export in GDP. In order to achieve this aim, we have to analyze position of tourism export in Uzbekistan in macro scale, finding key barriers, and problems of improvement, giving recommendation to further development.

Tourism industry is one of the main industries in Uzbekistan. Tourism industry contributed 3.4 % of GDP in 2022, which decreased due to COVID 19 tourism shock. Before pandemic, the number was 9,8% in 2019. Almost every region has potential for tourism export and business. However, opportunities are still staying under cover, due to lack of tourism infrastructure and experience of workers in the industry.

Following regions are the most iconic examples of touristic regions in Uzbekistan being under protection of UNESCO.

➤ **Bukhara** – being the main part of tourism industry of Uzbekistan, this region has 2 sites: religious and historical places. 60 % of people visiting the city come for religious purpose and seeing other sightseeing too. Other 40% comes for historical places and to enjoy the view. In

Bukhara there are more than 140 places included to UNESCO World Heritage, which attracts foreigners to enjoy ethnic tourism, gastronomic tourism, cultural tourism. City is dry and sunny, that's why the best season for tourists to visit is April-July, September to November.

- **Samarqand**- second touristic city. Humid and hot weather attracts tourists all over the world yearly, mostly purposes of ethnic tourism, gastronomic tourism, cultural tourism and historic monuments. This city is also under UNESCO.

- **Khorezm** – one of the main cities for cultural tourism and festivals. The region attracts average 1.5 million tourists every year, especially from neighboring countries.

- **Tashkent**- capital city and main part of business and medical tourism of Uzbekistan. Tashkent plays major role of transportation and commuting being the center of tourism infrastructure.

- **Karakalpakstan**- Main touristic place located in the region is Aral Sea. Region and committee of the country are trying to turn this place to eco-touristic location, in order to attract younger people of foreign countries.

“**Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan Regarding Tourism**” is considered as the main legal document to regulate tourism industry. Adopted by the Legislative Chamber on April 16, 2019 and approved by the Senate on June 21, 2019, this law consists of 10 sections and 45 articles. According to the law, for Uzbekistan there are 2 types of international tourism: inbound and outbound. The law is considered as the key relevant document in the industry, due to its brief definitions and regulations about licensing of tourism entities, tourist zones and clusters, tourism infrastructure and their components.

Among Central Asian countries, Uzbekistan stands as second in the terms of tourism export after Kazakhstan. Having a lot of opportunities, there is a potential to improve the situation of tourism export for making it number one in Central Asia.

As tasks are made by the government, it is important to study how much revenue Uzbekistan getting from tourism export. Number of visitors and which countries plays major role in exporting tourism to us.

Graph 1 Uzbekistan T&T GDP % (2015-2022)

Source: Compiled by author based on the data of World Bank, UNWTO and Ministry of Uzbekistan

As the line graph shows, over the past 7 years percentage of T&T GDP was approximately 5%. Until 2015, tourism GDP was between 4-5 % each year respectively with no much big difference, that is why, in the graph we tried to analyze the rest of the years from 2015 to 2022. From 2015 to 2018 GDP share was 5,4-6%, but this indicator fall down to 3,4% creating big loss

in GDP. However, in 2019 this percent skyrocketed, reaching to 9%. Because of Global COVID-19 pandemic, the rest 3 years faced again downward slope from 2% to 3,4 % in 2022.

Having numbers does not justify the act of saying tourism export is good or bad in our country. As we compared other regions and countries' tourism export in chapter 2, it is time to compare Uzbekistan and other Central Asian countries.

Graph.2 T&T GDP contribution of Central Asian countries (2017-2022)

Source: Compiled by author based on the information of Word Bank, UNWTO and OECD

As it was mentioned before, Uzbekistan comes 2nd in the share of tourism GDP share in Central Asia after Kazakhstan. Before pandemic, average tourism GDP was 10% in Kazakhstan, while this number is 4-5% for Uzbekistan. For both countries, pandemic dropped the indicator by 50% in 2020. By the time 2022 they again recovered from tourism decline, try to reach pre-pandemic numbers. After these 2, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan come behind with 4-5% of GDP share. The only problem for tourism export share is Afghanistan with political problems. The number stays within 0.3 not even reaching 1%. From outside, this seems like the country's problem only, while in reality it is the factor affecting other countries' tourism. As the political and social situation of Afghanistan is worsening, people are being afraid to choose other CE countries as destination. This is the result of having false information about other 4 CE countries. The biggest victim of Afghanistan's problem still is Uzbekistan, as for locating close to each other. That's is analyzing the situation in all CE countries together gives better concrete result for understanding the key points.

In order to see clearer numbers, we have to analyze how much tourism accounted for the overall export. As for the closed data problems, we would like to study only export share of tourism in Uzbekistan.

Graph.3 Share of tourism export on total export of Uzbekistan (in \$ billion)

Source: Compiled by author based on the data of World Bank, UNWTO

As Ministry of Tourism calculates, on average tourism export accounts for the 4-6% of the total export. Before 2020, export share of tourism was upward growing until 2019 it reached to almost 10%. However, as it was seen in other indicators, pandemic effected to tourism share too, dropping it to 2,6 %. For the economy of Uzbekistan, almost 3 times drop for tourism export share effected economic growth of the country too.

Graph.4 Tourism expenditure of Uzbekistan (in \$ billion)

Source: Compiled by author based on the data of World Bank and the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Before the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, revenue from tourism export were \$2.72 billion. On average, each visitors spent \$249 on their vacation in

Graph.5 The number of tourists visiting Uzbekistan from 1995-2021 (in million) people

Source: Compiled by author based on the data of World Tourism Organization

Uzbekistan. In 2020, tourist receipts plummeted due to the COVID-19 pandemic. From almost 3 billion dollars to \$422 million drop means almost 76 percent decrease in tourism expenditure. However, from 2022, tourism re opened for visitors again, while recovering from tourism shock step by step. If we analyzed how much money visitors spend in Uzbekistan during their travel, we have to study how many people arrive in our country. Is it enough for our touristic potential, or lower than planned? In the graph we can see the number of arrivals. The problem is number reaches to only 1-2 million people on average, while other CIS and CA countries accept visitors in 10 million or more. Highest number was seen during 2018 and 2019, being as the prosperity period for Uzbekistan's tourism. However, the number fall down triple after global pandemic. In 2022 5.2 million people arrived, which is the highest number after global pandemic shock on tourism industry.

As we can see number of arrivals to Uzbekistan is not as expected. There are several problems to tackle in in order to reach international standards. There are following **problems of tourism industry** of Uzbekistan:

1. 7 TEZs but not expected profit;
2. Public restroom facilities;
3. Low and expensive medical services;
4. Bad internet;
5. Inconvenient transportation;
6. Less sport events;
7. Opposite brain drain;
8. Less attraction of foreign students;
9. Inconvenient seasonality;
10. Inadequate marketing;
11. Scanty international events;
12. Exiguous number of amusement park;
13. Little number of water recreation areas;
14. Lack of tourism infrastructure and facilities (public bathroom, WC, transportation.)

In order to tackle these issues, we would like to suggest some recommendations on creation of resort areas.

1) An **ecovillage** is an intentional, traditional or urban community that is consciously designed through locally owned participatory processes in all four dimensions of sustainability (social, culture, ecology and economy) to regenerate social and natural environments. The problem is existing ecovillages are falsely understood and made just like a place in suburb to spend a weekend. After researching we analyzed that 4 states of Uzbekistan is highly available for ecovillages: Fergana, Samarqand, Namangan and Jizzakh. Probable image of recommended ecovillage see appendix table 4.

2) **Eco houses** – trend attraction tool in tourism after COVID 19, being popular in Northern Europe and South-West Asia. Eco houses are modern type of accommodation facility for tourists. People who intend to visit and stay at nature places would prefer it more than staying in busy central cities. As eco houses are supposed to locate in far from city, it will make people stay overnight, use extra transportation, creation of jobs as well.

3) **Vertical forest** – is an innovative residential skyscraper, aims to help biodiversity in the city, changing microclimate, saving species of plants and trees, improving eco condition of the specific area. This innovative building first started in Italy Milan named “Bosco Verticale”. The building changes the microclimate of the city by 3% in the beginning now making the air condition better than expected. Probable image of recommended vertical forest see appendix table 5.

4) **Ski resort**- one of the famous resort areas in Japan and UAE. In Japan this resort comes as a whole FTZ, named as Winter Village Zone, while in Dubai it is known for Ski Dubai Park. Serving all types of snow sports, adventure and exotic activities, it would help to attract young people more.

5) **Dessert nights** – having opportunity in Bukhara and Karakalpakistan, excursion of dessert night under open sky would be wonderful experience for youngsters. So far it is only widespread in UAE, attracting foreigners who wants to experience wild life nature.

6) **Theme parks** – opening famous parks, like “Walt Disney Park”, “Harry Potter village”, “Avengers city”, “Village of Santa Claus” or “Dancing Era” would be perfect example how European countries are leading in tourism export. It would help to accelerate our tourism export indeed.

7) **Water resort areas** – improving marketing of existing aqua parks and creating biggest water resort are in Central Asia would help to boost tourism export of young people.

1. **Improving** – this point includes direction of investment flow, joint project in the terms of FTZs and business environment. Uzbekistan current FTZs are not working profitably as expected like TEZs in foreign countries. Projecting joint programs in TEZs with other countries would benefit tourism export noticeably. Another point for joint project would be with Saudi Arabia for Muslim pilgrimage. In Islam, it is preferred to see and pay visit to 7 “Pir” before going to Haj and Umrah. If we make programs with them to attract people to Bukhara for known pilgrimage, it would boost tourism export. There are more recommendations to improve tourism export of Uzbekistan. They include technologic, informative and management changes.

Recommendation given above will help to improve tourism export in Uzbekistan, paving the way of reaching international ranks and standards. Creating and improving existing facilities as well as new resort areas will attract people all over the world increasing the share of tourism GDP.

REFERENCES

1. “Turizm to’g’risida”gi ORQ. (Qonun hujjatlari ma’lumotlari milliy bazasi, 19.07.2019-y., 03/19/549/3446-son; *Qonunchilik ma’lumotlari milliy bazasi*, 21.04.2021-y., 03/21/683/0375-son, 12.10.2021-y., 03/21/721/0952-son; 07.06.2022-y., 03/22/775/0477-son) <https://lex.uz/docs/-4428097>
2. UNWTO Promotes the Fight Against Poverty Through Tourism’, UNWTO NEWS Year XX, Issue 1 (2006), p. 9
3. See John Bendell & Xavier Font, ‘Which Tourism Rules? Green Standards and the GATS’, *Annals of Tourism Research*, Vol. 311, No. 1 (2001), pp. 139–56
4. www.worldbank.org - is the World Bank's premier compilation
5. http://www.unwto.org/newsroom/magazine/archives/news3_06_e.pdf ‘Tourism – The Path Ahead’, UNWTO NEWS Year XX, Issue 3. (accessed 30 May 2007), p. 6.
6. www.statista.com - Statista is a global data and business intelligence platform with an extensive collection of statistics, reports, and insights on over 80,000 topics from 22,500 sources in 170 industries.
7. www.oecd.org - The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
8. www.lex.uz - National database of legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan
9. www.stat.uz - The official website of the State Committee on Statistics of the Republic of Uzbekistan
10. <https://uzbektourism.uz/en> Ministry of Tourism and Culture in Uzbekistan